

Optical Transport Networks Enabling Security Features in 6G Systems

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Abstract *To support security features in 6G networks we propose an automated Moving Target Defence framework utilizing Live VM Migration, enabled by the optical transport network. Our experimental testbed optimizes VM migration scheduling to achieve enhanced security with minimal degradation of optical network performance.*

Introduction

The deployment of fifth-generation (5G) technologies, currently reshaping global communications, creates new opportunities across sectors, offering improved service delivery, resilience, and sustainability. To support these capabilities, 5G networks increasingly adopt disaggregation and virtualization across both Radio Access Network (RAN) and Core Network (CN) elements. The advent of Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) [1] accelerates this transformation, fostering open interfaces and multi-vendor interoperability, while cloud-native architectures facilitate the dynamic deployment of Network Functions (NFs) as Virtual Machines (VMs) or containers across edge and centralized clouds.

This paradigm shift introduces new requirements for transport networks, with heightened demands in bandwidth, service granularity, and latency guarantees. Optical networking technologies, such as flex-grid Dense Wavelength Division Multiplexing (DWDM), programmable photonic switches, and optical time-sensitive networking, are pivotal in addressing these challenges [2]. However, as networks move towards sixth-generation (6G) architectures, offering integrated communication, sensing, and computing capabilities, new dimensions of scale, autonomy, heterogeneity and security requirements emerge [3].

In this evolving landscape, virtualization and dynamic instantiation of NFs across distributed domains expose networks to an expanded attack surface. Decoupling of hardware and software, combined with the increased programmability of network elements, demands cybersecurity strategies that are adaptive, proactive, and embedded into the various network layers [4]. Among the promising approaches to enhance network security is Moving Target Defense (MTD) [5], which continuously alters the system's attack surface to complicate the efforts of potential attackers. MTD strategies in cloud-native environments typically focus on resource adaptation, either proactively or reactively to attack detection, with approaches including network address shuffling,

proxy reallocation, and live migration of virtualized resources. Several recent studies ([6]-[9]) have explored MTD's potential against Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks, demonstrating high effectiveness. However, a key challenge remains insufficiently addressed: the cost associated with such adaptations, particularly the impact of Live VM Migration (LVMM) on the underlying optical transport infrastructure.

In this paper, we study the use of the MTD approach to enable dynamic network protection over a 6G infrastructure. A cloud-based network is deployed, where multiple User Plane Function (UPF) nodes are interconnected to handle diverse user traffic demands. Security is enhanced by periodically relocating UPF resources through LVMM. The optical transport network plays a fundamental enabling role, providing the scalability, ultra-low latency, and fine-grained programmability needed to support real-time LVMM operations. However, frequent migrations can impose stringent capacity demands and degrade transport network performance. To better understand these effects, we conducted experimental measurements in a private 6G testbed, quantifying both the impact of cyber attacks on system throughput and the overhead introduced by LVMM on the optical transport network. Building on these insights, we developed an AI-based decision framework leveraging neural networks to forecast traffic patterns and optimize migration timing. This proactive mechanism ensures that migrations occur during low-utilization periods, effectively balancing security improvements with efficient resource management.

Security Considerations in B5G Systems

In the context of the virtualization reference architecture [10], the attack surface spans four distinct layers: the hardware layer, the host operating system (OS), the hypervisor, and the virtual machine (VM) layer. Attacks targeting the host OS

Figure 1: Network Architecture

layer are particularly critical, as they can compromise all VMs hosted on the affected system, including those running sensitive network functions. One promising countermeasure against such threats is VM migration-based MTD [11], where critical services - like the UPF - are shifted to different VMs without interrupting ongoing user interactions (see Fig. 1). Compared to network address shuffling and proxy-based approaches, VM live migration offers stronger protection by relocating the actual execution environment rather than simply obscuring network paths. This means that even if an attacker succeeds in identifying a target's IP address or proxy, the underlying service instance may have already been moved to a different physical or virtual host. This increases the attacker's cost, making it significantly more difficult to locate and compromise specific targets.

However, one question that arises regarding this technique is how often instances need to migrate across sites [12]. On one hand, VMs hosting critical NFs, must be migrated at regular intervals in order to efficiently avoid malicious acts. On the other hand, VM Migration execution requires large amounts of compute and network resources and thus may have a huge impact on the underlying transport network, leading to congestion and degraded performance if not carefully planned. In this context a challenge arises associated with achieving the security benefits of Live Migration MTD without compromising the 6G transport network performance.

In response to this, this study aims to identify an optimal trade-off between two competing objectives: maximizing the security gains by reducing the probability of a successful attack on the host OS, which could lead to the compromise or tampering of critical network functions such as the UPF, while minimizing the resource overhead and network strain introduced by frequent VM

migrations.

Experimental Platform Description

The 5G cloud testbed used in this work, relies on openstack private cloud software, which pools the resources into a virtualized cluster. The physical servers of the pool that host the VNFs are interconnected using optoelectronic switches.

This cluster provides the environment where 5G VNFs are deployed, hosted in VMs. For the deployment of the 5G network, free5gc is used for the core network segment and Open Air Interface (OAI) [13] is used for the RAN segment. The testbed supports a variety of network configurations, including RAN functional split, CP/UP split in the CN, CP NF isolation and the configuration of multiple network slices (NSs). An optical transport network connectivity between the various 5G RAN and Core elements has been used as shown in Fig 1.

Initial deployment, instantiation, reconfiguration and termination actions are automated through an open-source MANO platform based on Open-Source MANO (OSM) [14][15]. Furthermore, both physical and virtual hosts are interconnected to a Real-Time monitoring platform (Prometheus [16] and Grafana [17]) from which we can extract useful data related to network, compute, memory and storage resource consumption.

The proposed framework is executed in the following steps. First, the desired network topology is initiated through OSM. Network traffic is generated from UEs through iperf connections and based on real user traffic statistics. In this setup, the Automated MTD (AMTD) method is applied, where active VMs hosting 5G VNFs are periodically relocated to different physical hosts. To ensure service continuity provided from the 5G VNFs, we exploit the feature of LVMM offered by openstack. To quantify the LVMM impact on the transport network we perform block migration,

Figure 2: Impact of a SYN flood attack on the physical node hosting the UPF

which uses a pre-copy mechanism to initially transfer the VMs storage, and then in a series of synchronization iterations, transfers the memory state of the host. After successful execution of a migration, the TN-induced overhead and migration duration can be retrieved from the monitoring platform.

Numerical Results and Discussion

To quantify the impact of attacks on a 5G network we used a SYN flood targeting the physical node hosting the UPF VNF. A SYN flood attack is a form of Denial-of-Service (DoS) attack that targets the UPF, reducing the user throughput and degrading the overall performance of the network. As shown in Fig. 2, the attack led to a 70% throughput degradation, confirming the vulnerability of critical functions to cyber threats. Thus, the Expected Attack Damage (EAD) of an attack (as % of total throughput) is:

$$EAD(n) = 70\% \times AP(n)$$

where n is the number of migrations happening at each time interval and $AP(n)$ is the Attack Probability. Since migrations reduce the vulnerability of the system, we model the AP as:

$$AP(n) = e^{-k \times n}$$

where k is a fitting constant describing how fast more migrations lower the attack probability. Then, to assess the overhead introduced by LVMM, we captured the migration process using the monitoring platform (Fig. 3), allowing us to determine both the volume of data transferred and the duration of each migration event. The Migration Overhead (MO) of one UPF according to

Figure 4 : EAD vs MO trade-off

Figure 3: Live Migration of VM that hosts UPF.

Fig.3 is:

$$MO = (1Gbps \times 70s) + (0.5Gbps \times 30s) \approx 10.6GB$$

For the final 30 seconds, due to observed fluctuations, we assumed half the nominal throughput. We aimed to find a balance between the attack cost and the migration overhead, and to identify the optimal number of migrations that minimize the EAD while ensuring the optical transport network is not overloaded. As shown in Fig. 4, increasing the number of migrations reduces the EAD, but at the expense of increasing the migration overhead in the transport network.

To optimize the migration strategy, we implemented an LSTM-based forecasting model to predict the future traffic patterns and decide when to perform migrations. The model, written in Python using the Keras library, was trained using real user historic traffic data and was capable of forecasting the network's utilization over time. The output of the LSTM forecasting model is shown in Fig. 5. By using this model, we were able to schedule migrations during low-traffic periods, reducing the migration overhead and ensuring the network's performance remained stable. The prediction time horizon is aligned with the time required for migration, allowing sufficient lead time to optimize migration scheduling.

Figure 5 : Forecasting model output. Blue: raw data, yellow data: training set, green data: test set

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